

Proposal for a definition and formalisation of the *exaptation* concept

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1 Introduction

In 1972, Stephen Jay Gould and Elisabeth Vrba, wrote a seminal work where they were challenging the way of thought known as *adaptamentism* [3]. Adaptationism posits that any trait in an organism’s evolutionary trajectory, regardless of its origin, has always been and remains well-suited to its environment—a perspective suggesting that an adaptive explanation can always be found for the emergence of a trait. Though the amount of evidence that shows the power of an adaptationist explanation is remarkable and resists against epistemological attacks, as initially noted by Gould and Lewontin [2], and later emphasized by Gould and Vrba, it’s important to recognize that interpreting the function of traits solely through the lens of directional selection towards environmental adaptation can be misleading. This is because there are traits that serve no function at all.

To my knowledge, only one study has attempted to construct a formal methodology for identifying *exaptation* processes [1]. In this work, the authors developed a model utilizing the formalism of quantum mechanics to predict the potential repurposing of a given trait.

2 The model

In this section, I aim to illustrate the evolutionary history of an idealized organism, with the goal of determining whether its traits are adaptations or exaptations ¹. Let's start with the main character: an organism, denoted as O_1 , existing at time t_0 in a water environment, labeled as E_1 , possessing a genotype represented by $G = [g_1, g_2, g_3]$. This genotype encodes instructions for three functions: grayscale vision (g_1), nutrient absorption (g_2), and movement using barbels that follow water flow (g_3). These functions collectively enable the organism to survive and reproduce in its environment.

Now, let's introduce another species into the story. This species is characterized by predatory behavior; while it can subsist on other resources, it may also prey on O_1 , dissolving it for metabolism. These predators exhibit various colors, some of which are detectable by O_1 , while others fall outside its range of perception, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Environment E_1 with *predators* and O_1 organisms. The left panel shows t_0 , the right panel shows t_1 with O_2 organisms.

As we transition to time t_1 , we notice some of the organisms, denoted as O_1 , undergoing mutations resulting in variations in their functions. Specifically, some individuals gain the ability to perceive additional colors in the spectrum

¹The conceptual model develops along with an Agent-based model where to test the assumptions and conclusions.

(g_{1a}), others enhance their food storage capacity (g_{2a}), and some develop rigid barbels (g_{3a}). These new phenotypes are labeled as O_2 . In this scenario, the environment remains the original E_1 , with consistent nutrient levels and predators with varying hunting success based on their color, affecting their detectability. At time t_1 , it becomes uncertain which organism will exhibit the highest fitness. It could be the one with expanded vision to detect more predator types, or the one with increased nutrient storage capacity - more food equates to more energy for reproduction - or perhaps the one with enhanced defense mechanisms. All three phenotypes exhibit some level of adaptation to environment E_1 . However, consider a catastrophic event leading to the extinction of all predators, resulting in a shift to environment E_2 . In this new scenario, the three phenotypes possess different adaptations, and only one appears to be the most fit phenotype, likely the one capable of highest replication rates. As nutrient levels decrease due to the prolific feeding of the “great-feeders”, a new dynamic emerges. O_2 organisms with rigid barbels initiate attacks on other O_2 individuals, leading to the extinction of those with advanced color perception and a reduction in the population of the “great-feeders”.

My intention with this simplified and biased model is to demonstrate the possibility of establishing a framework from which we can derive two formalizable conclusions. The first function, denoted as $f(g_t)$, describes the evolution of traits from t_1 to t_2 . It represents a *novelty function*, contingent upon the chance emergence of mutational events. The second function, $f(g_e)$, maps the evolution of the traits’ tasks from environment E_1 to E_2 . It serves as an *exaptation* function, influenced by changes in environmental features.

In summary, we have a system of functions structured as follows:

$$f(g_t) : g(t_1) \rightarrow g(t_2)$$

$$f(g_e) : g(E_1) \rightarrow g(E_2)$$

A possible form as ODEs would represent the frequencies of the traits in

relation to time and to the environment characteristics:

$$(Trait_{exap, adap}) = \begin{cases} \frac{dg_t}{dt} = f(g_t) \\ \frac{dg_e}{dE} = f(g_e) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

3 Appendix

This is the first draft for a work proposal in the near future, so it does not have any intent to be considered as complete or rigorous. The model and mathematical formulation need serious improvement, along with conceptual analysis and the theoretical soundness of the research question.

References

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